

**Project: Fostering STEM inclusion among girls with migrant background:
the role of educational robots**

Report on WP8: Process and Outcome evaluation of ER intervention

1. Process evaluation

On overall, 9 junior secondary schools and 18 teachers have been involved in the project. Table 1 reports the number of schools and teachers recruited. In total, in December 2024 we recruited 11 schools and 22 teachers from Lombardy and Veneto, as planned in the research project. However, in March 2025, the number of schools dropped to 9 and the number of teachers to 18.

Table 1 - Schools and teachers recruited

	October 24			December 24			March 25		
	Lombardy	Veneto	tot	Lombardy	Veneto	tot	Lombardy	Veneto	tot
Schools	9	5	14	7	4	11	6	3	9
Teachers	20	13	33	12	9	22	10	8	18

In sum, the teachers have implemented the robot-supported STEM activities between December 2024 and May 2025, in line with the time schedule.

In the original proposal, the number of recruited teachers was set at 50 between Lombardy and Veneto. Unfortunately, we registered a dropout in the number of involved teachers due to: the teachers' heavy work-load from being involved in other concurrent PNRR activities; the lack of approval from the school board to implement the educational robotics activities in class; the difficulties in the involvement of classes in the data collection; and other inconveniences. The recruited schools are located in Lombardy and Veneto, in line with the aims of the project. The number of teachers and schools recruited is considered sufficient when running natural experiments to preliminary investigate the field of interest. Despite the dropouts, the project fulfills its main objectives.

A total of 285 children were involved in the robotics activities, of whom approximately 100 had a migrant background. By children with migrant background, we intend either children born outside Italy (first-generation immigrants) and children born to parents who have migrated (second-generation immigrants).

1.1 Robotic activities

Teachers were instructed to design a STEM-oriented educational activity involving coding a moving robot of their choice, for at least 10 hours during class. Beside those indications, teachers were let free to design the ER activities to be implemented in class. The teachers themselves, who best knew the children and their class group, designed and facilitated the activities. As a research team, we monitored the different aspects of the activities via online and face-to-face meetings with the teachers.

In this study, GROUP 1 used mBot, that is a pre-designed metal/plastic kit with essentially one constructive layout, whereas GROUP 2 used Lego Spike Prime kit, that is a modular robotic kit which allows a wide variety of layouts and can be built at every use. The two robots are similar in terms of programming as both robotic devices can be programmed either in a block-based language or in Python. Additionally, they are similar in terms of sensor equipment. However, mBot is a ready-to-use robot once built the first time, and it is less customizable as compared to Lego Spike Prime. The latter allows for better understanding of the different parts of the robot as the students can directly observe the sensors and actuators while building the robot.

1.1.1 Description of the robotics intervention with mBot

This group was involved in more complex programming and robotic activities such as reverse-engineering, followed by a reflection phase, as compared to GROUP 2. Specifically, the programme started with introductory and unplugged activities focused on understanding the role of precise instructions in controlling a robot. Students then engaged in pair-based block programming tasks using Blockly Games to learn core concepts such as sequencing, loops, and conditional statements. Subsequently, students worked with Scratch to design simple interactive projects and to practise code analysis through reverse-engineering tasks. The intervention concluded with hands-on robotics activities using mBot, during which students programmed the robot to solve distance-based and maze-navigation challenges, gradually integrating sensors and conditional logic. The programme ended with a short reflection phase to support consolidation of learning.

1.1.2 Description of the robotics intervention with Lego Spike Prime

Using LEGO SPIKE Prime, students engaged in activities that combined robot construction and block-based programming. The first phase consisted of unplugged and visual programming activities focused on computational thinking and algorithmic reasoning. Initial tasks focused on assembling a basic robot structure and programming simple movements (e.g., forward motion, turns, geometric paths), followed by activities involving distance and colour sensors. Students worked in stable, heterogeneous groups throughout the programme. Peer tutoring by older students supported group work and facilitated learning. The intervention emphasised hierarchical thinking, sequencing of instructions, and

collaborative problem solving. The intervention adopted a flexible design, allowing task simplification when needed, and conceptualised error as a constructive element of learning.

2. Outcome evaluation

2.1 Data collection

An online questionnaire was administered to the students attending the involved classes, before (T0) and after (T1) the robotics activities, with the supervision of their teachers during classes. The data collection was implemented in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Italian Psychological Association and privacy regulations. The approval of the ethics committees of the Universities of Bergamo and Milano-Bicocca and the consent of parents was obtained prior to data collection. This was done first before the ER activities began (between November 2024 and February 2025, T0) and then again at the end of the activities (between March and June 2025, T1). The aim was to check for any changes in scores between the two administrations.

2.2 Construction of the questionnaire

Questionnaire investigated: STEM engagement (Burack, et al., 2019; Kier et al., 2014) selected in WP1; STEM-related gender stereotype (Ertl et al., 2017; McGuire et al. 2022) selected in WP3; acculturation process (Nigbur et al., 2008) and cultural identity measure (Mezzich et al., 2009) selected in WP4.

Burack, C., Melchior, A., & Hoover, M. (2019). Do after-school robotics programs expand the pipeline into STEM majors in college?. *Journal of Pre-College Engineering Education Research (J-PEER)*, 9(2), 7.

Ertl, B., Luttenberger, S., & Paechter, M. (2017). The impact of gender stereotypes on the self-concept of female students in STEM subjects with an under-representation of females. *Frontiers in psychology*, 8, 703.

McGuire, L., Hoffman, A. J., Mulvey, K. L., Hartstone-Rose, A., Winterbottom, M., Joy, A., ... & Rutland, A. (2022). Gender stereotypes and peer selection in STEM domains among children and adolescents. *Sex Roles*, 87(9), 455-470.

Mezzich, J. E., Ruiperez, M. A., Yoon, G., Liu, J., & Zapata-Vega, M. I. (2009). Measuring cultural identity: Validation of a modified Cortes, Rogler and Malgady Bicultural Scale in three ethnic groups in New York. *Culture, Medicine, and Psychiatry*, 33(3), 451-472.

Nigbur, D., Brown, R., Cameron, L., Hossain, R., Landau, A., Le Touze, D., ... & Watters, C. (2008). Acculturation, well-being and classroom behaviour among white British and British Asian primary-school children in the south-east of England: Validating a child-friendly measure of acculturation attitudes. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 32(6), 493-504.

2.3 Results

Before the ER activities at T0, we collected 190 questionnaires in 5 schools and 10 classes. The sample was composed of 88 female, 99 male, and 3 others. As for their socio-cultural background, 112 were Italians and 78 had a migrant background.

Once collected data from both T0 and T1 questionnaires, we carried out the first preliminary analyses, starting with descriptive statistics and frequencies using SPSS software. After verifying the quality and completeness of the dataset, the final sample included 128 girls/boys, with an average age of 11.77 years (min = 10, max = 15), 59 boys and 67 girls (1 person answered “Other” and another “I prefer not to answer”). Eighty-three were of Italian origin and the remaining 45 had a migrant background, specifically the sample included 42 Italian boys, 42 Italian girls, 19 migrant boys, and 25 migrant girls. In addition, 38 students had never done robotics before. Out of the remaining 79 students who had some previous experience with robotics, 7 had already practiced it at school, 7 outside of school, and 4 both at school and outside of school.

Subsequently, t-tests were carried out to observe any differences between the pre- and post-test scores relating to various dimensions: interest in science and mathematics (STEM interest), interest in jobs that use science and mathematics (interest in STEM careers), enjoyment of science and mathematics lessons (STEM enjoyment), ability to do science and mathematics homework (STEM self-efficacy), and gender stereotypes related to STEM subjects.

Paired t-test showed no significant differences between pre and post for:

- STEM interest: science interest: $t(127) = .00$; $p = 1$; math interest: $t(127) = .14$; $p = .89$,
- STEM enjoyment: enjoyment for science lesson: $t(127) = .36$; $p = .72$; enjoyment for math lesson: $t(127) = .93$; $p = .36$;
- STEM self-efficacy: self-perceived ability to do science homework: $t(127) = .36$; $p = .72$; self-perceived ability to do math homework: $t(127) = .98$; $p = .33$;
- interest in STEM careers: interest in career in science $t(127) = .72$; $p = .48$; interest in career in math $t(127) = .52$; $p = .61$.

As for STEM gender stereotype, some significant differences emerged. After the activity, students decreased their beliefs that boys generally are good in science/technology/mathematics ($t(127) = 2.32$, $p = .02$). The same applies to the belief that girls generally are good in science/technology/mathematics ($t(127) = 2.21$, $p = .04$).

Then, we performed moderation analysis to investigate the role of possible moderators such as gender and level of prior robotic experience. As for participant gender, math interest scores varied according to gender, with a greater increase from pre- to post-test for girls than for boys ($R^2 = .53$; $b = -.52$, $SE = .14$, $t = 3.85$, $p = .0002$). The same trend was observed for interest in jobs that use mathematics ($R^2 = .31$, $b = .34$, $SE = .16$, $t = 2.2$, $p = .03$). Similarly, STEM gender stereotypes were moderated by gender. The belief that “Mathematics/science/technology are subjects more for girls than Italian” increased significantly more for girls than for boys ($R^2 = .23$; $b = .53$, $SE = .16$, $t = 3.3$, $p = .0013$), and the same applies for 'I think girls are usually good at science/technology/mathematics' ($R^2 = .18$, $b = .38$, $SE = .17$, $t = 2.3$, $p = .0229$).

Another moderator identified was robotics experience: whether or not the girls/boys had participated in other robotics activities in the past moderated their interest in mathematics ($R^2 = .73$, $b = -.36$, $SE = .16$,

$t = -2.29, p = .0239$). In particular, students who had no previous experience showed a greater increase in interest in mathematics than students who did have previous experience, perhaps due to a sort of “wow effect” linked to the novelty of the activity.

As for the subsamples of Italian students and students with a migrant background, two specific trends emerged. In the Italian subgroup, students gender moderated the interest in mathematics ($R^2 = .52, b = .73, SE = .18, t = 3.97, p = .0002$). Specifically, math interest increased among Italian girls, whereas it did not increase among Italian boys. Furthermore, in the sub-sample of students with migrant background, interest in science increased more among boys than among girls ($R^2 = .43, b = -.49, SE = .21, t = -2.34, p = .0242$).

Among the possible explanations for those results, we suggest that: (1) duration of ER activities (10 hours) was too little to produce a remarkable impact on students’ engagement; (2) the measurement tools were not sensitive enough to detect a relevant change among the students. Future studies should implement longer ER projects (at least 20 hours/year) to test the idea that more extended activities would have a stronger impact on the children’s STEM engagement. Additionally, future studies could use validated scales to measure students’ self-efficacy in robotics (e.g., Agus et al., 2025; Tsai et al., 2021).

Agus, M., Marras, A., & Negrini, L. (2025). The Italian Version of the Robotics Learning Self-Efficacy Scale (RLSES-IT): Assessment of psychometric features in a sample of young students. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 11, 101646.

Tsai, M. J., Wang, C. Y., Wu, A. H., & Hsiao, C. Y. (2021). The development and validation of the robotics learning self-efficacy scale (RLSES). *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 59(6), 1056-1074.

Moreover, future studies could implement a more “ecologic” approach to the involvement of children with migrant background by investigating the role of families and broader STEM gender stereotypes on STEM engagement.

2.4 Logbooks from teachers

In order to gain the teachers’ point of view on the experience and to allow teachers to critically reflect on their experience, they were asked to fill out a logbook covering the following main points:

- Before the activity: main objectives and motivations, expected skills among children, which activities and robotic kit they intend to use and why; their hopes, fears, expectations;
- After the activity: what happened in class, paying attention to positive and negative aspects, differences from the plan, level of achievement of objectives, level of interest of the participating students, how the group work went, how the groups were structured and their dynamics, any particular incidents;
- Once the work was completed, process evaluation of the activities: review of timing, content, methods, choice of robot, choice of activities, etc., and personal critical reflections on the activities.

According to teachers, the objectives of robotics experiences were: to stimulate interest and motivation in robotics and STEM subjects, to enhance computational thinking, and to encourage collaborative learning. The expected skills were: understanding programming as a means of controlling a robot;

recognizing the value of sequentiality and logic in coding; knowing how to use visual or textual programming environments (e.g., Scratch, Blockly); developing problem-solving strategies and debugging skills; creating simple algorithms to control robotic actions; working in groups to tackle challenges and design creative solutions; strengthening deductive and analytical reasoning by observing the robot's behavior in relation to the code.

At the end of the activity, the teacher reported that the educational robotics course was very engaging and positive, highlighting the collaboration and cohesion of the class. The playful and challenging approach of the activities encouraged involvement and shared responsibility, and also engaged students with different cognitive styles and abilities. They referred that teamwork, creativity, and flexibility were promoted.

The critical issues encountered were: technical problems such as programming or assembly, that can cause frustration among students; the activities required more time than ordinary school hours; the lack of shared observations and self-assessment tools; gender segregation during some activities with some girls focusing more on the creative part than on programming; the workshop generated noise and disorder in the school environment, preventing other teachers to join in and collaborate in the robotics activities.

Conclusions: The educational robotic projects provided a safe and stimulating environment for exploring STEM skills, developing collaboration, logic, and confidence. In order to strengthen the educational impact, teachers suggested to:

- introduce debriefings and guided reflections, especially for girls;
- break down more complex activities into progressive steps;
- improve the assessment of the activities with shared observational tools.

Overall, educational robotics is confirmed as a powerful and inclusive methodology.

3. Overall evaluation of the research project

The entire process was relatively straightforward and had several positive points, but also some minor weak points.

On the positive side, it is worth noticing the pre-post design involving two measurements, one pre-activity and one post-activity, which allowed for sound comparison to test any significant changes. This is in line with the natural experiment methodology, where the exposure to the event of interest, that is robot-supported activities, has been implemented within a real-world environment where those processes naturally operate, such as school classrooms and has not been manipulated by the researcher (Leatherdale, 2019; Crane et al., 2020). In addition, the sample of students was balanced in terms of gender and included a good proportion of girls/boys with a migrant background.

One element that strengthened the work was the use of both quantitative and qualitative measures: on one hand, a self-report questionnaire focused on the girls' and boys' perceptions and experiences was administered to students, and on the other hand the observations of the teachers were collected via teachers' logbooks. This made it possible to cross-reference and integrate the various results and will allow for more in-depth analysis and more structured reflections for future researches.

With regard to the critical aspects, we must acknowledge the difficulty to monitor the process of administering the pre- and post-questionnaires, which was managed entirely by the teachers. This resulted in the difficulty to obtain two questionnaires for each student, resulting in missing data in either the pre- or post-intervention data collection. As a result, it was not possible to include the entire initial sample in the data analysis, but only the part that included both assessments. In addition to this, there was an initial dropout by the teachers involved, due to school commitments and difficulties in managing this additional workload.

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